

DERMATOFITOZLARNING ZAMONAVIY DIAGNOSTIKA USULLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA: Microsporia pilaris teri va soch follikularini zararlovchi qo‘ziqorin kasalligi bo‘lib, asosan bolalar orasida uchraydi. Ushbu maqolada 4 yoshli qiz bolaning klinik kuzatuv natijalari taqdim etiladi. Bemorning bosh sohasida soch to‘kilishi va qichishish kabi shikoyatlari mavjud bo‘lgan. Dermatologik tekshiruv natijasida o‘choqli shikastlanish aniqlanib, Yog‘och chiroq yordamida lyuminesstent diagnostika o‘tkazilgan va Microsporum canis qo‘ziqorini ajratilgan. Kombinatsiyalangan antifungal terapiya bilan muvaffaqiyatli davolash natijasida bemor klinik tiklanishga erishgan. Ushbu maqola Microsporia pilarisni erta aniqlash va samarali davolash usullari bo‘yicha muhim ma‘lumotlarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Microsporia pilaris, dermatofitoz, Yog‘och chiroq, lyuminesstent diagnostika, Microsporum canis, antifungal terapiya, klinik kuzatuv, mikologik tekshirish, dermatologiya, bolalar infeksiyalari.

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ДЕРМАТОФИТОЗОВ

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АННОТАЦИЯ: Microsporia pilaris – это грибковое заболевание, поражающее кожу и волосяные фолликулы, которое чаще всего встречается у детей. В данной статье представлены результаты клинического наблюдения за 4-летней девочкой. У пациентки наблюдались жалобы на выпадение волос и зуд в области головы. Дерматологическое обследование выявило очаговые поражения, была проведена люминесцентная диагностика с помощью лампы Вуда, и выделен грибок Microsporum canis. Благодаря успешному лечению комбинированной антимикотической терапией пациентка достигла клинического выздоровления. Данная статья предоставляет важную информацию о методах раннего выявления и эффективного лечения Microsporia pilaris.

Ключевые слова: Microsporia pilaris, дерматофитоз, лампа Вуда, люминесцентная диагностика, Microsporum canis, антимикотическая терапия, клиническое наблюдение, микологическое исследование, дерматология, детские инфекции.

MODERN METHODS OF DIAGNOSING DERMATOPHYTOSES

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ABSTRACT: Microsporia pilaris is a fungal infection that affects the skin and hair follicles, most commonly found in children. This article presents the results of a clinical observation of a 4-year-old girl. The patient complained of hair loss and itching on the scalp. Dermatological examination revealed focal lesions, and fluorescent diagnostics using Wood's lamp identified the fungus *Microsporum canis*. Successful treatment with combined antifungal therapy led to the patient's clinical recovery. This article provides important information on methods for early detection and effective treatment of *Microsporia pilaris*.

Keywords: *Microsporia pilaris*, dermatophytosis, Wood's lamp, fluorescent diagnostics, *Microsporum canis*, antifungal therapy, clinical observation, mycological examination, dermatology, pediatric infections.

KIRISH

Microsporia – dermatofit qo‘ziqorinlari sabab bo‘ladigan yuqumli kasallik bo‘lib, asosan bolalar orasida uchraydi. Kasallikning yetakchi etiologik omillari *Microsporum canis* va *Microsporum audouinii* qo‘ziqorinlari hisoblanadi. Infeksiya manbai odatda uy hayvonlari, ayniqsa mushuklar va itlar bo‘lib, kasallik yaqin aloqa orqali yuqadi. Bosh sohasida hosil bo‘ladigan dumaloq, aniq chegaralangan, sochlarning sinishi bilan kechadigan shikastlanishlar kasallikning tipik klinik belgilari hisoblanadi. Diagnostikada asosiy usullardan biri Yog‘och chiroq yordamida lyuminesstent tekshirish bo‘lib, bu usulning soddaligi va yuqori informativligi uni amaliyotda keng qo‘llashga imkon beradi. Ushbu maqolada *Microsporia pilaris*ning klinik kuzatuv, diagnostik yondashuvlar va samarali davolash usullari ko‘rib chiqiladi.

MAQSAD. Ushbu ishning maqsadi *Microsporia pilaris* bilan kasallangan bemorning klinik kuzatuv natijalarini taqdim etish, diagnostik usullar, xususan, Yog‘och chiroq tekshiruvining ahamiyatini tahlil qilish va samarali davolash taktikasini muhokama qilishdan iborat.

MATERIALLAR VA USULLAR. Tadqiqot ambulator sharoitida olib borildi. Bemor: 4 yoshli qiz bola (onasi hamrohligida) bosh sohasida soch to‘kilishi shikoyati bilan dermatologga murojaat qilgan. Anamnezdan: bemor kasallikni bir oy oldin mushukcha bilan aloqa qilganidan so‘ng yuqtirgan. Mushukcha veterinar tomonidan davolangan. Oila anamnezi bo‘yicha dermatofit infeksiyalari aniqlanmagan. Tekshirish usullari: Vizual tekshiruv: Boshning oksipital sohasida 3,5-4 sm o‘lchamdagi, aniq chegaralangan, sochlar 3-4 mm masofada sinib ketgan, un sepilgandek oq qobiq bilan qoplangan o‘choq aniqlandi. Yog‘och chiroq diagnostikasi: Bosh terisining zararlangan sohasi ostida yorqin yashil lyuminesstentsiya aniqlandi. Mikroskopik tekshirish: Fokusdan qirqma olinib, mikroskop ostida tekshirilganda, patogen qo‘ziqorin sporalari aniqlangan. Bakteriologik tekshirish: Madaniyat tekshiruvida *Microsporum canis* ajratilgan

NATIJALAR VA MUHOKAMA. Tekshiruv natijalari *Microsporia pilaris* tashxisini tasdiqladi. Qiz bola ambulator sharoitda qo‘ziqorinlarga qarshi kombinatsiyalangan terapiya bilan davolandi. Jadval 1. Bemorda qo‘llanilgan davolash rejimi

Dori vositasi	Dozalash rejimi	Davomiylilik
Terbinafin (tashqi)	Kuniga 2 mahal	4 hafta
Grizeofulvin (og‘iz orqali)	Kuniga 10 mg/kg	6 hafta
Antiseptik eritma	Kuniga 2 mahal	4 hafta

Davolash fonida 4 hafta ichida kasallik klinik remissiyaga erishdi, 6 haftadan so'ng esa qo'ziqorin madaniyati to'liq negativ natija berdi. Oila a'zolari va aloqada bo'lgan shaxslar tekshirildi, ularda infeksiya aniqlanmadi.

XULOSA. Yog'och chiroq dermatologiyada qo'ziqorin infeksiyalarini aniqlashda 90 yildan ortiq vaqtdan beri samarali diagnostik vosita bo'lib kelmoqda. Uning soddaligi va mavjudligi sababli klinik amaliyotda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Microsporia pilaris diagnostikasida lyuminesstent tekshiruv usuli, mikroskopiya va madaniyat tekshiruv bilan birgalikda qo'llanilishi aniqlikni oshiradi. Ushbu tadqiqot klinik kuzatuv asosida bemorlarni samarali davolash va infeksiyani.

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